

Brain Manifestations of Six Mental Elements in Neuropsychanalysis

Zi-Jian Cai

CaiFortune TriL Consulting, Number 129, Building 6, Room 404,
North Dongwu Road, Suzhou City, Jiangsu Province, 215128, PR China

Abstract

Background: It was added the reticular noradrenergic(NA), serotonergic(5-HT), dopaminergic(DA) and acetylcholinergic (ACh) systems to regulate sleep and emotional balance among unconscious (emotions) / preconscious (memories) / conscious in Freudian topographic theory for depression and anxiety, while it was added by Cai the reticular DA and ACh systems to schizophrenia in Freudian structural theory of id (motivation) / ego (selfishness) / superego (knowledge), with these reticular systems altogether termed as the fourth element "reticula" for neuropsychanalysis.

Purpose: It was attempted to unify the classification of elements in neuropsychanalysis as the world people expecting.

Methods: It was searched the papers from Pubmed and Baidu, and then classified and summarized.

Results and Discussions: (a) It is classified superego(knowledge) in structural theory to memories in topographic theory. (b) In schizophrenia, it is suggested that the elevated DA in associative striatum integratively inhibit the memories-associated comprehension of perception, compatible with the downstream hypoconnectivity between prefrontal-limbic cortices and thalamic nuclei, whereas the opposite assumption wrong as activation of associative striatum by DA would correct memories, improve comprehension and ameliorate schizophrenia following repetition of reward/punishment. (c) It is the schizophrenic hyperconnectivity between somatomotor cortex and thalamic nuclei that indicates overactivation of simple ego action, while schizophrenic hyperconnectivity between auditory network and thalamic nuclei that represents alteration of perception including hallucination. (d) In depression, it is divided the emotional balance into aversion and motivation, while conscious into perception and behavior(including ego). (e) In depression, it is unbalanced in limbic activities, sleep and NA/5-HT/DA.

Conclusions: It is classified the neuropsychanalysis into six elements as aversion/motivation/perception/behavior/memories/reticula, unified for depression and schizophrenia.

Introduction

Freud formulated the psychoanalytic theories with the interactions and conflicts among the three psychological mental elements as unconscious / preconscious / conscious in topographic theory [1,2], and id / ego / superego in structural theory [3], integrative and intuitive to depict various psychological processes of whole brain.

The neuropsychanalysis is the scientific neurobiological basis of psychoanalysis [4,5]. To investigate the three Freudian psychological mental

elements by science, Cai corresponded the Freudian concepts of unconscious/preconscious/conscious in topographic theory to the closest neuropsychological concepts as emotions/memories/conscious [1,2], and the id/ego/superego of Freudian structural theory to motivation/selfishness/knowledge [3,6], respectively. As supplements, it was added to neuropsychanalysis the ascending noradrenergic(NA), serotonergic (5-HT) and acetylcholinergic (ACh) systems to differentiate the waking and sleep in regulation of the emotions / memories / conscious (or unconscious / preconscious /

More Information

How to cite this article: Cai Z-J. Brain Manifestations of Six Mental Elements in Neuropsychanalysis. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(6):142-7.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(6).18

Keywords:

Perception,
Behavior,
Emotion,
Memory,
Reticular formation.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

conscious) in depression [1], while recent reviews further supplemented the ascending dopaminergic (DA) system to depression and anxiety [7]. In parallel, Cai likewise added the DA and ACh systems directly to motivation / selfishness / knowledge (or id / ego / superego) for schizophrenia [3]. Recently, Cai further classified these ascending NA, 5-HT, DA and ACh systems altogether as the fourth element reticula for neuropsychanalysis [6], supplementing the three emotions / memories / conscious (or unconscious / preconscious / conscious) elements and three motivation / selfishness / knowledge (or id / ego / superego) elements of psychoanalysis.

However, the division of Freudian psychoanalysis into topographic theory and structural theory is not convenient. In this article, it is attempted to unite altogether the elements in topographic theory and structural theory, and to formulate a unified classification of neuropsychological elements for neuropsychanalysis, which is the expectation of many world people in television. Besides, it is further supported the unified classification of elements in neuropsychanalysis with their anatomical, neuropsychological or neuroimaging manifestations in brain.

Methods

For this complex and interdisciplinary subject, integrative review of progressions in related subfields was the best and most convincing method. Meta-analysis only fit investigation of a specific topic in a well-studied subfield, and not for the broad integrative classification here. Besides, it was certainly more important to analyze and integrate the collected reviews and new research papers from several fields by classification, comparison and summarization.

Paper search was mainly performed on Pubmed and Baidu Xueshu. The first preference was given to relevant updated reviews. If there was no appropriate updated review, then the relevant reviews published at more than 10 years ago were allowed for citation. If there was neither appropriate old review, then the research articles with repeated experimental results were collected for citation.

The words adopted in the search of papers were listed as the followings: (a) Psychoanalysis; (b) ego; (c) id; (d) schizophrenia; (e) dopamine; (f) imaging; (h) depression, and so on. Usually, two or more of these words were combined in usage for search, such as (a) ego schizophrenia, (b) dopamine schizophrenia, (c) imaging schizophrenia, (d) depression serotonin, (e) imaging depression, and so on.

Results and Discussions

Combination of Element Superego to Memories

Superego is the mental element in Freudian structural theory for schizophrenia, corresponding to the closest neuropsychological concept as knowledge [3,6].

Preconscious is the mental element in Freudian topographic theory for depression and anxiety, and corresponding to the closest neuropsychological concept as memories [1,2,6].

Because knowledge is a portion of memories, herein it is obviously easy to classify superego into the concept of memories. In anatomy and neuropsychology, memories are stored as synaptic plasticity along the neural pathways processing the corresponding information [1,2].

Neuroimaging Studies of DA in Schizophrenia

For schizophrenia, it was recently supplemented the ascending DA and ACh systems to the Freudian structural theory [3,6], with DA overall selective on superego(knowledge and comprehension), excitatory or disinhibitory to id(motivation) and beneficial to ego(selfishness) including habits and procedural memories [3].

In neuroimaging studies, it was detected the reticular DA as increased in associative striatum in schizophrenia [8,9]. Because the memories-associated comprehension, herein as a part of superego in association with perception, is associative in nature, the associative striatum is a suitable brain site for relay of the memories-associated comprehension to thalamic and prefrontal regions for plan and action [10]. The elevated DA in associative striatum fits the integrative inhibition on relay of the memories-associated comprehension by reticula element in schizophrenia [10].

On the other hand, if it is assumed in opposite that the elevated DA could integratively activate the associative striatum, it would increase the influence of memories and comprehension to prefrontal-limbic and thalamic regions. After repetition of reward and punishment in society, the corrected memories and improved comprehension resulting from DA activation of associative striatum would correct the wrong mind and behavior not adaptive to society, and ameliorate rather than cause the symptom of schizophrenia. Therefore, this opposite assumption is wrong.

It is noted that some authors classified the DA in ventral tegmental area(VTA) to the reward output of pleasure as a part of id(motivation) [11]. However, considering the importance of reticular NA, 5-HT, ACh in psychiatry in parallel to reticular DA, it is obviously appropriate to classify all reticular projections including NA, 5-HT, ACh and DA as element reticula [6]. It is widely accepted that the reticular DA is integratively activated by subcortical id(motivation) for relay to the forebrain [7,11,12].

Neuroimaging Studies of Hypoconnectivity in Schizophrenia

Besides, neuroimaging studies also found the hypoconnectivity between prefrontal-limbic cortices and thalamic nuclei [13,14,15], consistently in

association with basal ganglia in schizophrenia [14]. Because the relay of memories-associated comprehension by associative striatum to thalamic and prefrontal-limbic regions is suppressed by reticular DA, it certainly decreases the activity of prefrontal-limbic cortices from thalamic nuclei [10]. However, a part of ego as simple selfish action beyond the influence of memories-associated comprehension remains within the prefrontal and motor cortices while not affected [10]. This part of ego contains those directly driven by id(motivation) originating unconsciously from hypothalamus and brainstem as appetites for food [12,16], sex [17,18], water [19] and so on.

As mentioned above, because improvement of memories and comprehension from repetition of reward and punishment in society may behaviorally correct the wrong mind and action of schizophrenia, the integrative inhibition in associative striatum by elevated DA is required for the symptoms of schizophrenia, even though DA may inhibit multiple inhibitory interneurons to accomplish such integrative function. The downstream hypoconnectivity between prefrontal-limbic and thalamic regions in schizophrenia [13,14,15] is compatible with the integrative inhibitory role of elevated DA to associative striatum in influencing the thalamic and prefrontal-limbic regions.

Neuroimaging Studies of Hyperconnectivity in Schizophrenia

Neuroimaging studies in schizophrenia as well revealed the hyperconnectivity between primary-sensorimotor cortices and thalamic nuclei, such as somatomotor cortex, primary auditory network and so on [13,14,15]. The hyperconnectivity also extended consistently to basal ganglia in schizophrenia [14].

The hyperconnectivity between somatomotor cortex and thalamic nuclei obviously indicates the overactivation of simple action as a part of selfish ego in schizophrenia. Whereas, the hyperconnectivity between primary auditory network and thalamic nuclei represents the elevated primary perception and even hallucination of auditory information in schizophrenia [14].

Perception as New Mental Element for Neuropsychanalysis

As mentioned, the connectivity between primary auditory network and thalamic nuclei represents the primary auditory perception. It is not id as motivation, nor ego as selfish plan and action, nor superego as knowledge and memories, nor reticula as ascending reticular formation. In other words, perception is not among the four elements in neuropsychanalysis.

Figure 1: The Classification of Mental Elements in Neuropsychanalysis for Schizophrenia

However, auditory perception is altered as hyperconnectivity between primary auditory network and thalamic nuclei in schizophrenia [13,14,15], manifesting as the psychotic symptom like auditory oversensitivity and even hallucination [14], which must be considered for the disease, beyond the four

available elements in neuropsychanalysis. Due to this requirement, herein it is further added the “perception” as the fifth element in neuropsychanalysis, representing the altered perception including auditory network in schizophrenia.

Figure 1 outlines the classification of mental elements to id (motivation) / ego (selfishness) / perception / superego (memories) / reticula in neuropsychanalysis for schizophrenia.

Sleep, Neuroimaging and Biochemical Studies in Depression

In depression, the ascending NA, 5-HT, and ACh systems differentiate in their discharge and result in waking, slow wave sleep(SWS) and rapid eye movement(REM) sleep [1], with the REM sleep processing emotional memories and shifting the emotional balance toward depression [1,2], while the SWS functioning in reverse to restore the emotional balance disrupted by accumulated emotional memories in waking [1,2].

In diagnosis, the disturbances of SWS result in the unbalance of emotions in depression from accumulation of emotional memories in waking and REM sleep [1,2], while excessive REM sleep can not only accumulate emotional memories, but also reduce muscle tone of motivation, both of which can result in depression [2].

In neuroimaging detection, it was revealed the hippocampus, amygdala, medial prefrontal and cingulate cortices as mostly affected brain regions in depression [20,21,22], the brain structures for both emotions and memories. Specifically, in depression it was found volumetric reductions in insula, superior temporal gyrus, inferior frontal gyrus, anterior cingulate cortex, amygdala, hippocampus, and thalamus [20,21], abnormal activation in ventromedial frontal regions, the anterior cingulate and amygdala [22], and hyperconnectivity of dorsolateral prefrontal cortex in frontoparietal network [20].

Meanwhile, postmortem and biochemical studies found decrease in 5-HT, NA, and DA as relevant to depression and anxiety [7]. For brain manifestations of depression, it is necessary to consider not only the affected brain structures for emotions and memories revealed by neuroimaging detection, but also the biochemical reduction in NA/5-HT/DA.

Division of Element “Conscious” for Neuropsychanalysis in Depression

It is noted that the mental element “conscious”, meaning as wisdom and appropriateness, has not been corresponded with appropriate neuropsychological concept. Herein, enlightened by five mental elements for schizophrenia, it is obvious that conscious can be better understood if appropriately divided. Accordingly, it is suggested to divide conscious into two elements as perception and behavior, in which perception can form comprehension when associated with memories, while behavior can encompass element ego in Freudian structural theory.

In neuroimaging detection, formation of comprehension from perception in association with

memories manifested in depression as the volumetric reductions in insula, superior temporal gyrus, amygdala, hippocampus, and thalamus [20,21], as well as abnormal activation in amygdala [22]. These are all brain structures responsible for both emotional feelings and memories.

Element behavior manifested in depression as the volumetric reductions in inferior frontal gyrus, anterior cingulate cortex, and thalamus [20,21], and abnormal activation in ventromedial frontal regions and anterior cingulate [22], as well as the hyperconnectivity of dorsolateral prefrontal cortex in frontoparietal network [20].

Division of Element “Unconscious” for Neuropsychanalysis in Depression

As mentioned in Introduction, it has been corresponded the neuropsychological concept emotions to element unconscious in Freudian topographic theory for depression and anxiety [1,2,6], while the neuropsychological concept motivation to element id in Freudian structural theory for schizophrenia [3,6]. Because emotions encompass motivation, it is obviously easy to classify motivation into emotions. However, fear and sadness are often adopted in depression and anxiety [1,2,6], which is opposite to motivation.

Due to the necessity of these two opposite parts of emotions in psychiatry, motivation for schizophrenia [3,6] while fear/sadness for depression and anxiety [1,2,6], it is obvious important to retain these two forms of emotions. In this regard, herein it is divided the neuropsychological concept emotions(or element unconscious) into two elements as aversion and motivation, in which aversion includes fear, sadness, stress, pain and so on, while motivation includes appetitive drive for food, water, sex and so on.

Conclusions

In this article, it is attempted to unify the classification of mental elements in neuropsychanalysis, overcoming the inconvenience for separation of Freudian psychoanalysis into topographic theory and structural theory, as expected by the world people in television.

Superego as knowledge in structural theory is attributed to element memories in topographic theory. In schizophrenia, the increase in DA in associative striatum integratively inhibits the activity of this region, and inhibits its function for relay of superego as the memories-associated comprehension, resulting in the downstream hypoconnectivity between prefrontal- limbic cortices and thalamic nuclei. However, the opposite assumption for DA to integratively activate the associative striatum would correct memories, improve comprehension and ameliorate schizophrenia following repetition of reward and punishment in society, which is obviously wrong.

On the other hand, the hyperconnectivity between somatomotor cortex and thalamic nuclei indicates the overactivation of simple ego as somatomotor action. Whereas, the hyperconnectivity between auditory network and thalamic nuclei represents the alteration of auditory perception in schizophrenia, manifesting as psychotic symptom like auditory oversensitivity and even hallucination.

For brain manifestations of depression, the hippocampus, amygdala, superior temporal gyrus, medial prefrontal and cingulate cortices, thalamus and related brain structures for emotions and memories are affected, along with the alteration of sleep and reduction in biochemical NA/5-HT/DA.

In depression, it is divided the element conscious into perception and behavior, in which perception forms comprehension when associated with memories, while behavior encompasses element ego in Freudian structural theory. Brain manifestations of comprehension by perception in association with memories lie in superior temporal gyrus, hippocampus, amygdala, and thalamus, while brain manifestations of behavior in medial prefrontal and cingulate cortices, as well as thalamus.

In depression, it is also divided the element unconscious(emotions) into two opposite elements, aversion and motivation.

Summarized altogether, there are six elements as aversion/motivation/perception/behavior/memories/reticula in neuropsychanalysis, unified for both schizophrenia and depression. It is expected this work to promote investigations on brain manifestations of elements in neuropsychanalysis.

Limitations

The interactions among elements illustrated in this article and in Figure 1 only represent a part of their complicated interactions. These interactions are highlighted in this article because they help define and classify the elements as the purpose of this article. Obviously more complicated interactions are required to work out and more related investigations are necessary in future.

Imaging detection of brain in schizophrenia is diverse, various and complicated. In this paper, it is adopted the associative hypoconnectivity between prefrontal- limbic and thalamic regions, and hyperconnectivity between somatomotor, auditory and thalamic regions, along with basal ganglia of associative striatum with elevated DA. These are the integrative and net interactions among these brain regions, with details of plausible multiple excitatory and inhibitory connections not determined.

Besides, activation of self appraisal is another possible result for the increase of DA in striatum, which counteracts against the knowledge and comprehension. As memories-associated

comprehension can correct wrong behavior, it is necessary to inhibit the memories-associated comprehension in schizophrenia. It is uncertain about whether such inhibition of memories-associated comprehension by DA in striatum of schizophrenia is directly accomplished by inhibitory interneurons there, or is indirectly by activation of the counteracting self appraisal. Obviously, it is required for more investigations.

Authors' Information

Zi-Jian Cai (Orcid: 0000-0003-2378-5034) as the author of this paper is now the supervisor of CaiFortune TrIL Consulting in Suzhou City, PR China. The author is a theoretical scientist on neuropsychology, aging/development and physics unification, and is also a social activist, independent publishing many papers abstracted in CNKI and Scopus.

Author's Contributions

The sole one author responsible for all of this article.

Source of Financial Funding

The author declares no financial support to this work.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflicts of interests in writing this article.

References:

- [1] Cai Z-J. Progressions of sleep, memory and depression applicable to psychoanalysis: A review. *Curr Psychiatry Rev* 2016 Jul; 12(3): 240-245. Doi: 10.2174/1573400512666160610083505.
- [2] Cai Z-J. Evolution of psychoanalytic interactions and conflicts in vertebrates. *Sleep Hypn.* 2018 Mar; 20(1):1-7. Doi: 10.5350/Sleep.Hypn.2016.18.0128.
- [3] Cai Z-J. The dopaminergic and acetylcholinergic supplements to Freudian structural theory of psychoanalysis. *OALib J.* 2021 Jul; 8(7): e7603. Doi: 10.4236/oalib.1107603.
- [4] Salone A, Di Giacinto A, Lai C, et al. The interface between neuroscience and neuropsychanalysis: Focus on brain connectivity. *Front Hum Neurosci.* 2016 Feb; 10: 20. Doi: 10.3389/fnhum.2016.00020.
- [5] Johnson B, Flores Mosri D. The Neuropsychanalytic approach: Using neuroscience as the basic science of psychoanalysis. *Front Psychol.* 2016 Oct; 7: 1459. Doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01459.
- [6] Cai Z-J. Freudian three elements in psychoanalysis needs the fourth element reticula. *Taiwan J Psychiatry.* 2023 Jun; 37(2): 97-98. Doi: 10.4103/TPSY.TPSY_17_23.
- [7] Liu Y, Zhao JP, Guo WB. Emotional roles of mono-aminergic neurotransmitters in major depressive disorder and anxiety disorders. *Front Psychol.* 2018 Nov; 9: 2201. Doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02201.
- [8] Kesby JP, Eyles DW, McGrath JJ, et al. Dopamine, psychosis and schizophrenia: the widening

gap between basic and clinical neuroscience. *Transl Psychiatry*. 2018 Jan; 8(1): 30. Doi: 10.1038/s41398-017-0071-9.

[9] Weinstein JJ, Chohan MO, Slifstein M, et al. Pathway-specific dopamine abnormalities in schizophrenia. *Biol Psychiatry*. 2017 Jan; 81(1): 31-42. Doi: 10.1016/j.biopsych.2016.03.2104.

[10] Cai Z-J. Neuropsychanalytic prerequisite for diagnosis of psychiatric unbalance. *Int J Psychiatr Res*. 2023 Jul; 6(4): 1-2. Doi: 10.33425/2641-4317.1168.

[11] Chenu A, Tassin J-P. Pleasure: Neurobiological conception and Freudian conception. *Encephale*. 2014 Apr; 40(2): 100-7. Doi: 10.1016/j.encep.2013.06.003.

[12] Campos A, Port JD, Acosta A. Integrative hedonic and homeostatic food intake regulation by the central nervous system: Insights from neuroimaging. *Brain Sci*. 2022 Mar; 12(4): 431. Doi: 10.3390/brainsci12040431.

[13] Giraldo-Chica M, Woodward ND. Review of thalamocortical resting-state fMRI studies in schizophrenia. *Schizophr Res*. 2017 Feb; 180:58-63. Doi: 10.1016/j.schres.2016.08.005.

[14] Avram M, Brandl F, Bäuml J, et al. Cortico-thalamic hypo- and hyperconnectivity extend consistently to basal ganglia in schizophrenia. *Neuropsychopharmacol*. 2018 Oct; 43(11): 2239-2248. Doi: 10.1038/s41386-018-0059-z.

[15] Tu P-C, Lee Y-C, Chen Y-S, et al. Network-specific cortico-thalamic dysconnection in schizophrenia revealed by intrinsic functional connectivity analyses. *Schizophr Res*. 2015 Aug; 166(1-3): 137-43. Doi: 10.1016/j.schres.2015.05.023.

[16] Berthoud H-R. Metabolic and hedonic drives in

the neural control of appetite: who is the boss? *Curr Opin Neurobiol*. 2011 Dec; 21(6): 888-96. Doi: 10.1016/j.conb.2011.09.004.

[17] Bittoni C, Kiesner J. When the brain turns on with sexual desire: fMRI findings, issues, and future directions. *Sex Med Rev*. 2023 Sep; 11(4): 296-311. Doi: 10.1093/sxmrev/qead029.

[18] Stoléro S, Fonteille V, Cornélis C, et al. Functional neuroimaging studies of sexual arousal and orgasm in healthy men and women: a review and meta-analysis. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev*. 2012 Jul; 36(6): 1481-509. Doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2012.03.006.

[19] McKinley MJ, Denton DA, Ryan PJ, et al. From sensory circumventricular organs to cerebral cortex: Neural pathways controlling thirst and hunger. *J Neuroendocrinol*. 2019 Mar; 31(3): e12689. Doi:10.1111/jne.12689.

[20] Brandl F, Weise B, Bratec SM, et al. Common and specific large-scale brain changes in major depressive disorder, anxiety disorders, and chronic pain: a transdiagnostic multimodal meta-analysis of structural and functional MRI studies. *Neuropsychopharmacol*. 2022 Apr; 47(5): 1071-1080. Doi: 10.1038/s41386-022-01271-y.

[21] Zacková L, Jáni M, Brázdil M, et al. Cognitive impairment and depression: Meta-analysis of structural magnetic resonance imaging studies. *Neuroimage Clin*. 2021 Sep; 32: 102830. Doi: 10.1016/j.nicl.2021.102830.

[22] Kerestes R, Davey CG, Stephanou K, et al. Functional brain imaging studies of youth depression: a systematic review. *Neuroimage Clin*. 2013 Dec; 4: 209-31. Doi: 10.1016/j.nicl.2013.11.009.

